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Effectiveness of Alternative Learning System (ALS) Teachers in Bayugan City Division: Inputs to a Proposed Intervention Program

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Abstract.

This study aimed to determine the level of effectiveness of Alternative Learning System (ALS) teachers as perceived by both ALS learners and teachers in terms of instruction, classroom environment, and professional responsibilities. Using a descriptive-comparative research design, data were gathered from ALS learners and teachers through structured questionnaires. Results revealed that ALS teachers were rated Very Effective across all three domains. In the area of instruction, learners rated their teachers with an overall weighted mean of 2.74, while teachers rated themselves slightly higher at 2.94. Regarding the classroom environment, learners gave a mean rating of 2.68, whereas teachers reported a perfect mean of 3.00, emphasizing their strong focus on safety, respect, fairness, and active participation. For professional responsibilities, learners provided a mean rating of 2.72 and teachers 2.89, indicating consistent adherence to professional duties. The Mann-Whitney U Test showed no significant difference between learners' and teachers' perceptions of professional responsibilities but revealed substantial differences in instruction and classroom environment. Furthermore, data on student outcomes indicated an overall retention rate of 60.5% and a completion rate of 38.7%, highlighting challenges in sustaining learner engagement and program completion. The study concluded that ALS teachers consistently demonstrate effectiveness in instruction and in maintaining a conducive learning environment. However, discrepancies between learners' and teachers' perceptions suggest areas for reflection and professional growth. Strengthening instructional strategies and fostering collaborative, learner-centered practices are recommended to enhance retention and completion rates, thereby improving the overall impact of the ALS program on out-of-school youth and adult learners.

Keywords: ALS, Retention Rate, Completion Rates, Instruction Ratings, and Classroom Environment

1.0 Introduction

Education serves as the cornerstone of inclusive growth, driving social progress and sustainable development. However, despite ongoing global initiatives to expand access to learning, millions of youths remain excluded from education. According to UNESCO, about 250 million students and young people were still out of school in 2023, an increase of six million compared to 2021.

This rise is partly attributed to the continued exclusion of many adolescent girls from education systems and the overall stagnation in global educational progress. As UNESCO data indicate, barriers such as poverty, gender inequality, and limited educational resources continue to hinder the realization of equitable and quality education for all.

This education crisis has affected marginalized categories of people, especially in countries where poverty and conflict, as well as provision for quality education, are still a challenge. UNESCO pointed to innovative and flexible learning systems to respond to the diverse requirements of non-traditional learners (e.g., adults, dropouts, remote, etc.) towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG).

To address these problems, the Philippines established the Alternative Learning System (ALS), a second-chance education opportunity, specifically for out-of-school youth. However, according to a process evaluation study by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), ALS has received only 0.1% of the Department of Education's budget while serving only 0.8% of basic education learners. This results in high learner-teacher ratios, limited resources, and inadequate infrastructure, which affect the effectiveness of ALS.

A related World Bank (2020) study indicated alarmingly low participation rates and completion rates for ALS. In 2017, less than 10% of the estimated 6.6 million learners aged 15-30 who were potentially eligible for ALS enrolled, and approximately 20% of those who enrolled passed the Accreditation and Equivalency (A&E) test. These findings reflected significant issues in program implementation, learner motivation, and instructional support.

In the local context, specifically in Bayugan City Division, Agusan del Sur, ALS teachers encounter many challenges that hinder their effectiveness. They struggle with inadequate personal resources for teaching materials, endure poor teaching conditions, and face the burden of long travel to reach their mostly distant learners. These issues significantly impact their enthusiasm. While these educators display remarkable resilience, they must receive organized and structured support to optimize their commitment and enhance their teaching activities fully.

Therefore, this study sought to assess the effectiveness of ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division, identifying gaps and opportunities that could inform the design of a proposed intervention program. Therefore, this assessed the effectiveness of ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division, identifying gaps and opportunities that could inform the design of a proposed intervention program.

This situation needs to be addressed by considering the implications and explorations of the study. It is essential to examine further the capacity-building needs, training opportunities, and contextualized intervention programs for ALS teachers. Implementers of ALS would greatly benefit from well-planned program monitoring and support systems that include professional development. Additionally, fostering collaborative skills transfer would significantly enhance their capabilities and effectiveness in teaching within non-formal learning environments.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive comparative research design, which was defined as a method that systematically described a population, situation, or phenomenon without manipulating variables. It aimed to answer the "what" of the subject under investigation by collecting quantifiable information that could be used to describe aspects of a given population or situation statistically. Descriptive research did not delve into the cause-and-effect relationship but focused on providing a detailed snapshot of conditions as they naturally occurred.

2.2 Research Locale

This study was conducted in Bayugan City, Agusan del Sur's only city, known for its agricultural productivity and thriving cut-flower industry. Bayugan City served as a regional center in the Caraga region, with a diverse population engaged mainly in farming and small-scale trade. The study specifically focused on the five barangays within Bayugan City: Poblacion, Taglatawan, Noli,

Mabuhay, and San Juan. These barangays were selected due to their active engagement in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) program and represented a mix of urban and rural communities.

Bayugan City covered an area of approximately 688.77 square kilometers, with a population of 109,499 based on the 2020 Census. The chosen barangays varied in geographic and socio-economic characteristics, providing a broad perspective of the ALS learners' profiles and learning environments within the city. This setting offered a representative context for examining the effectiveness of ALS teachers and the outcomes of learners in diverse community settings.

2.3 Research Participants

The population of this study consisted of individuals involved in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in the Bayugan City Division, specifically ALS teachers and learners who were actively participating during the academic year. The respondents came from five barangays where ALS was implemented, namely Noli, Poblacion, Taglatawan, Mabuhay, and San Juan. The teacher respondents were licensed ALS teachers assigned to facilitate community-based and flexible learning sessions. In contrast, the learner respondents included out-of-school youth, working adults, and other marginalized individuals who pursued education through non-traditional pathways. As reflected in Table 1, a total of 213 respondents participated in the study, with Teacher J having the highest frequency (30 or 14.08%), followed by Teacher F (26 or 12.21%) and Teacher C (24 or 11.27%). The remaining respondents were fairly distributed among Teachers A, B, D, E, G, H, and I, with percentages ranging from 7.04% to 10.80%. This distribution indicates a balanced representation of ALS participants, providing sufficient data to assess the effectiveness of ALS instruction within the Bayugan City Division.

2.4 Research Instrument

The study utilized two survey questionnaires as the primary research instruments: one intended for ALS learners and the other for ALS teachers. Both questionnaires were anchored on Charlotte Danielson's Framework for Teaching but were carefully contextualized to suit the Alternative Learning System (ALS) setting. The instruments covered three key domains, namely: Instruction, Classroom Environment, and Professional Responsibilities.

The learner's questionnaire consisted of statements that measured how students perceived their teacher's effectiveness in terms of delivering lessons, maintaining a positive learning environment, and fulfilling professional duties. Meanwhile, the teachers' questionnaire focused on their own teaching practices and responsibilities as ALS facilitators.

Each questionnaire employed a three-point Likert scale with the options: Always, Sometimes, and Rarely. This scale was intentionally kept simple to make it more appropriate and easily understood by the respondents, considering their diverse backgrounds and varying literacy levels.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research instruments, both questionnaires were subjected to content validation by a panel of experts in Alternative Learning System (ALS) implementation and educational research. The panel consisted of the Division Education Focal Person, who had undergone extensive training and professional development related to the ALS program, and master teachers from the ALS program of Bayugan City Division. Their expertise and experience were instrumental in evaluating the relevance, clarity, and alignment of the questionnaire items with the study objectives, ensuring that the instruments accurately measured the intended variables. After validation, the reliability of the instruments was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, that indicate a high level of internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire items.

After validation, a tryout test was conducted with a separate group of students who were not part of the actual study respondents. The results of the tryout test were analyzed to determine the clarity, reliability, and internal consistency of the items. Necessary revisions were made based on the

findings before the final administration of the questionnaires.

In addition to survey data, the researcher also examined the retention and completion records from the previous school year of the same teacher-respondents to support the findings and provide a more comprehensive picture of teacher effectiveness in the ALS context.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

Before the actual data collection, a letter of permission was sent to the ALS Focal Person to seek approval to conduct the study in the selected barangays: Noli, Poblacion, Taglatawan, Mabuhay, and San Juan. Upon approval, coordination with the ALS mobile teachers in each barangay was conducted to facilitate the distribution and retrieval of the research instruments.

The researcher personally administered the validated questionnaire to a total of 213 ALS students under the supervision of the 10 selected ALS teachers. The students were identified and selected based on their respective class sizes using Slovin's formula to ensure a representative sample. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants, and informed consent was obtained to ensure voluntary participation.

Data on learners' retention and completion rates were collected using a data-gathering form provided by the ALS Registrar, which was based on the official records for the school year 2025–2026. These records reflected the actual participation and progress of ALS learners, showing how many continued their learning throughout the program and how many completed it. This information provided a clear picture of learner engagement and achievement within the Alternative Learning System, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of instructional delivery and the overall implementation of the ALS program in the Bayugan City Division.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical standards to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants involved. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from ALS teachers and learners, clearly explaining the purpose of the study, procedures involved, and their right to participate or withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly observed by ensuring that no names, personal identifiers, or sensitive information appeared in the research instruments, records, or reports. All data collected was used solely for academic and research purposes and was securely stored to prevent unauthorized access. Special consideration was given to ALS learners, recognizing their diverse backgrounds and vulnerabilities, by conducting the study in a respectful and non-discriminatory manner. The study also ensured that participants were not exposed to any physical, psychological, or social harm, and that the findings were reported honestly and accurately without misrepresentation or bias.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings on the level of effectiveness of ALS teachers as perceived by both students and teachers in the areas of instruction, classroom environment, and professional responsibilities. The results were analyzed to identify strengths and areas for improvement in ALS teaching practices, focusing on their impact on student engagement, retention, and completion rates. The subsequent tables provided a detailed breakdown of the perceived effectiveness in each domain and offered insights into the alignment of teacher practices with student experiences.

3.1 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Instruction

Table 3.1 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Instruction

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
My teacher asks each of us questions to reflect on what we learned	2.89	0.372	Always	Very Effective
My teacher repeats or explains difficult parts of the lesson clearly.	2.84	0.441	Always	Very Effective
My teacher makes sure we understand one part of the lesson before moving to the next.	2.79	0.460	Always	Very Effective
My teacher does not rush but gives us enough time to understand the topic.	2.78	0.469	Always	Very Effective
My teacher guides us when our answers are not correct.	2.70	0.602	Always	Very Effective
My teacher repeats or explains difficult parts of the lesson clearly.	2.69	0.634	Always	Very Effective
My teacher asks each of us questions to reflect on what we learned	2.69	0.595	Always	Very Effective
My teacher makes sure we understand one part of the lesson before moving to the next.	2.69	0.546	Always	Very Effective
My teacher does not rush but gives us enough time to understand the topic.	2.69	0.539	Always	Very Effective
My teacher guides us when our answers are not correct.	2.62	0.600	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.74	0.260	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Table 3.1 presents the perceived level of effectiveness of ALS teachers in terms of Instruction, as rated by ALS students. The indicators focus on how teachers deliver lessons, facilitate understanding, and support learners during the instructional process.

Based on Table 3.1, the item with the highest weighted mean is "My teacher asks each of us questions to reflect on what we learned" (mean = 2.89), indicating that ALS teachers are highly effective in using questioning strategies to check understanding and foster active participation. Field observations show that when learners are prompted to reflect, they become more engaged; such reflection helps them think critically and recall details, making discussions more meaningful. Recent studies support this finding, emphasizing that effective questioning techniques encourage learner reflection and interaction, which lead to higher engagement and more profound understanding (Cabual, 2023; Francisco, 2024). Similarly, research in alternative learning settings highlights that learners are more motivated and participative when teachers create opportunities for reflection and collaborative discussion (Andres & De Guzman, 2024).

The findings revealed that while ALS teachers were generally rated as very effective in instructional practices, the provision of corrective feedback emerged as the weakest area, with the lowest weighted mean of 2.62. This suggests that although teachers did provide feedback when learners gave incorrect answers, the explanations were often brief and insufficient, limiting learners' understanding of their mistakes. Observations further showed that some learners felt hesitant to ask for clarification, contributing to the lower rating. Research supports this result, indicating that feedback lacking clarity and depth can lead to learner disengagement and repeated errors (Idulsa & Luzano, 2024), while rushed or unexplained corrections may increase anxiety and reduce participation (Lalanan

& Oco, 2025). Despite this gap, the overall weighted mean of 2.74, interpreted as Very Effective, reflects that ALS teachers consistently used questioning strategies to involve learners and sustain engagement actively. However, the imbalance between strong questioning practices and less detailed feedback suggests missed opportunities for deeper learning. As emphasized by Cuario et al. (2024), questioning and feedback function best as interconnected practices; questioning stimulates thinking, while feedback consolidates understanding. Thus, the results indicate that although learner engagement was effectively initiated through questioning, the learning cycle was not always fully completed due to limited feedback depth, underscoring the need to strengthen corrective feedback to enhance comprehension and learner confidence.

3.2 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Classroom Environment

Table 3.2 *Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Classroom Environment*

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
My teacher treats all learners fairly and equally.	2.80	0.425	Always	Very Effective
My teacher reminds us to behave and act properly wherever we are during ALS sessions.	2.78	0.479	Always	Very Effective
There is mutual respect between my teacher and fellow learners.	2.76	0.563	Always	Very Effective
I feel safe and respected in our learning sessions.	2.75	0.551	Always	Very Effective
My teacher listens to our concerns or feedback.	2.75	0.522	Always	Very Effective
Our learning environment is kept clean and orderly.	2.70	0.527	Always	Very Effective
I feel comfortable expressing myself during lessons.	2.63	0.580	Always	Very Effective
Our community learning center is free from distractions during our learning sessions.	2.58	0.629	Always	Very Effective
My teacher encourages teamwork during learning activities.	2.57	0.630	Always	Very Effective
I am encouraged to ask questions and share my ideas.	2.46	0.710	Sometimes	Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.68	0.270	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

As shown in Table 3.2, the overall weighted mean of 2.68 (SD = 0.270) indicates that ALS teachers are always very effective in creating a positive classroom environment. The highest-rated indicators, fair and equal treatment of learners ($\bar{x} = 2.80$) and promotion of proper behavior ($\bar{x} = 2.78$), highlight teachers' emphasis on inclusivity, discipline, and respect, which supports a safe and motivating learning climate. Indicators related to mutual respect, feeling safe, listening to learners, and maintaining an orderly environment (means ranging from 2.70 to 2.76) further affirm that ALS teachers foster emotionally and physically supportive spaces conducive to learning. However, the lowest-rated indicators encouraging teamwork ($\bar{x} = 2.57$) and encouraging learners to share ideas ($\bar{x} = 2.46$) suggest areas for improvement in promoting collaboration and learner voice. Overall, the findings confirm that ALS teachers effectively establish safe and respectful learning environments, while highlighting the need to strengthen participatory and collaborative classroom practices to enhance learner engagement further.

3.3 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Professional Responsibilities

Table 3.3 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Students in Terms of Professional Responsibilities

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
My teacher comes on time during learning sessions in our community.	2.84	0.396	Always	Very Effective
My teacher continues the session even if there are only a few learners.	2.83	0.455	Always	Very Effective
My teacher talks respectfully and listens when we share concerns.	2.77	0.491	Always	Very Effective
My teacher wears proper and decent attire when teaching.	2.75	0.477	Always	Very Effective
My teacher encourages us to finish the ALS program and take the A&E Test.	2.74	0.613	Always	Very Effective
My teacher returns our outputs and gives feedback.	2.73	0.598	Always	Very Effective
My teacher informs us about ALS-related activities or schedules from barangay meetings.	2.69	0.564	Always	Very Effective
My teacher keeps our personal stories or problems private.	2.65	0.632	Always	Very Effective
My teacher explains to us what we missed when we are absent.	2.64	0.621	Always	Very Effective
My teacher gives reminders about our tasks even outside class hours.	2.62	0.708	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.72	0.287	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Based on Table 3.3, the overall weighted mean of 2.72 (SD = 0.287) indicates that ALS teachers are always very effective in fulfilling their professional responsibilities, reflecting strong commitment, responsibility, and professionalism. The highest-rated indicators, punctuality ($\bar{x} = 2.84$) and continuing sessions despite low attendance ($\bar{x} = 2.83$), highlight teachers' dedication and inclusivity. High ratings for respectful communication, proper attire, and encouraging program completion (means ranging from 2.74 to 2.77) further affirm their professionalism and motivational role. The lowest-rated indicators, confidentiality, explaining missed lessons, and providing reminders outside class hours (means from 2.62 to 2.65), though still very effective, suggest areas for strengthening communication and follow-up support. These results indicate that while teachers consistently meet professional standards, additional structured mechanisms for learner follow-up may further enhance support for irregular attendees. Strengthening after-class communication and individualized guidance may help address learning gaps caused by absences. Overall, the findings confirm that ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division demonstrate strong professionalism and dedication, with clear opportunities to improve the continuity of learner support further.

3.4 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Instruction

Table 3.4 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Instruction

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
I explain lessons clearly and in a way that is easy for learners to understand.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I ask questions to check if learners understand the lesson.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I modify my teaching methods when learners seem confused.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I ask each learner questions to help them reflect on what they have learned.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I make sure learners understand one part of the lesson before moving to the next.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I guide learners when their answers are incorrect or incomplete.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I review the previous lesson before introducing a new topic.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I clearly explain or repeat difficult parts of the lesson.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I give learners time to think before they answer questions.	2.80	0.422	Always	Very Effective
I avoid rushing and give enough time for learners to absorb the lesson.	2.80	0.422	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94	0.070	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Based on Table 3.4, the overall weighted mean of 2.94 with a standard deviation of 0.070 indicates that ALS teachers in Bayugan City Division are rated as “Always Very Effective” in terms of instruction. This suggests that they consistently employ effective teaching strategies that promote learner understanding, engagement, and mastery of lessons. The highest-rated indicators “I explain lessons clearly and in a way that is easy for learners to understand,” “I ask questions to check if learners understand the lesson,” “I modify my teaching methods when learners seem confused,” “I ask each learner questions to help them reflect on what they have learned,” “I make sure learners understand one part of the lesson before moving to the next,” and “I guide learners when their answers are incorrect or incomplete” all obtained a perfect weighted mean of 3.00, demonstrating a strong instructional foundation among ALS teachers.

These findings align with Flores and Caluza (2024), who emphasized that the clarity of lesson delivery and the ability to adjust teaching strategies according to learner needs are key predictors of learning success in flexible education programs like ALS. Likewise, Rivera (2023) highlighted that questioning and feedback are vital components of effective instruction, as they promote learner reflection, engagement, and deeper comprehension skills that are essential in the alternative learning environment where learners have diverse educational backgrounds.

Meanwhile, the slightly lower-rated indicators, “I review the previous lesson before introducing a new topic” ($\bar{x} = 2.90$) and “I clearly explain or repeat difficult parts of the lesson” ($\bar{x} = 2.90$), still fall under the “Very Effective” category, indicating that teachers maintain strong lesson continuity and reinforcement strategies. This aligns with Delos Santos and Ramos (2022), who found that consistent lesson review strengthens learners’ retention and confidence, especially for adult and returning learners in ALS. The lowest yet still “Very Effective” items, “I give learners time to think

before they answer questions” and “I avoid rushing and give enough time for learners to absorb the lesson” (both $\bar{x} = 2.80$), suggest that while teachers value pacing, some may still face time constraints in meeting curriculum demands or learner schedules.

This finding is consistent with Cuario et al. (2024), who emphasized that ALS instruction thrives when teachers integrate learner-centered and adaptive strategies tailored to diverse learner needs. Likewise, Rosales and Javier (2022) underscored that differentiated Instruction in ALS is vital in addressing varying learner profiles and sustaining participation. These insights reinforce the present results by showing that instructional effectiveness in ALS is strongly tied to how teachers adjust their methods in real time. While pacing remains an area for continued attention, the overall findings confirm that ALS teachers successfully demonstrate instructional adaptability that benefits learner engagement and understanding.

Overall, the data reveal that ALS teachers exhibit exceptional instructional competence, demonstrating adaptability, clarity, and responsiveness to learners’ needs. These qualities align with DepEd’s (2023) emphasis on learner-centered instruction under the ALS K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, underscoring that effective teaching in ALS hinges on flexibility, reflection, and clear communication to ensure that every learner progresses meaningfully.

3.5 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Classroom Environment

Table 3.5 *Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Classroom Environment*

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
I ensure that learners feel safe and respected during learning sessions.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I treat all learners fairly and equally.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I maintain a clean and orderly learning environment.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I encourage learners to ask questions and share their ideas.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I promote teamwork and collaboration during learning activities.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I make sure that the CLC is free from distractions to ensure focused learning sessions.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I listen actively to the learners’ concerns and feedback.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I model and promote mutual respect between me and my learners.	2.80	0.422	Always	Very Effective
I help learners feel comfortable expressing themselves during lessons.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I consistently remind learners to demonstrate proper behavior wherever ALS sessions are held.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94	0.084	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Based on Table 3.5, ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division demonstrate a very high level of effectiveness in creating a positive and inclusive classroom environment, as reflected by an overall

weighted mean of 2.94, interpreted as “Always Very Effective.” The highest-rated indicators ensuring learners feel safe and respected, treating learners fairly, maintaining a clean and orderly learning space, minimizing distractions in the Community Learning Center, and actively listening to learners’ concerns each obtained a perfect mean of 3.00, highlighting teachers’ strong commitment to inclusivity, safety, and learner-centered management. These findings align with studies emphasizing that safe, respectful, and equitable learning environments enhance learner engagement, motivation, and attendance in alternative education settings.

Indicators related to encouraging learner participation, teamwork, open expression, and proper behavior ($\bar{x} = 2.90$) further show that ALS teachers foster interaction, collaboration, and accountability. Meanwhile, the slightly lower yet still very effective rating for modeling mutual respect ($\bar{x} = 2.80$) suggests a minor area for strengthening relational dynamics. Overall, the results affirm that ALS teachers effectively establish supportive, inclusive, and collaborative classroom environments that serve as a strong foundation for sustained participation and holistic learning among out-of-school youth and adult learners.

3.6 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Classroom Environment

Table 3.6 *Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Classroom Environment*

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
I ensure that learners feel safe and respected during learning sessions.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I treat all learners fairly and equally.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I maintain a clean and orderly learning environment.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I encourage learners to ask questions and share their ideas.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I promote teamwork and collaboration during learning activities.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I make sure that the CLC is free from distractions to ensure focused learning sessions.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I listen actively to the learners’ concerns and feedback.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I model and promote mutual respect between me and my learners.	2.80	0.422	Always	Very Effective
I help learners feel comfortable expressing themselves during lessons.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I consistently remind learners to demonstrate proper behavior wherever ALS sessions are held.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94	0.084	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Based on Table 3.6, ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division demonstrate a very high level of effectiveness in creating a positive and inclusive classroom environment, with an overall weighted mean of 2.94, interpreted as “Always Very Effective.” The highest-rated indicators ensuring learners feel safe and respected, treating learners fairly and equally, maintaining a clean and orderly learning environment, keeping the CLC free from distractions, and actively listening to learners’ concerns each

obtained a perfect mean of 3.00, reflecting strong adherence to inclusive, learner-centered practices consistent with UNESCO (2023) and DepEd (2023) principles.

Indicators related to encouraging learner participation, teamwork, open expression, and proper behavior ($\bar{x} = 2.90$) further show that ALS teachers promote interaction, collaboration, and accountability. The slightly lower yet still very effective rating for modeling mutual respect ($\bar{x} = 2.80$) suggests a minor area for strengthening relational dynamics. Overall, the findings affirm that ALS teachers effectively establish safe, supportive, and collaborative learning environments that foster engagement and serve as a strong foundation for sustained participation and holistic learning among out-of-school youth and adult learners.

3.7 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Professional Responsibilities

Table 3.7 Level of Effectiveness of the ALS Teachers as Perceived by the ALS Teachers in Terms of Professional Responsibilities

Indicators	Wtd Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
I continue the session even if only a few learners attend.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I return learners' outputs and give timely feedback.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I keep learners' personal stories or problems private.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I wear proper and decent attire when teaching.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I encourage learners to complete the ALS program and take the A&E Test.	3.00	0.000	Always	Very Effective
I come on time during learning sessions in the community.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I listen to learners and speak respectfully when they share concerns.	2.90	0.316	Always	Very Effective
I inform learners about ALS-related activities or schedules from barangay meetings.	2.80	0.422	Always	Very Effective
I give reminders about tasks even outside of official class hours.	2.70	0.483	Always	Very Effective
I explain the lesson to learners who were absent.	2.60	0.516	Always	Very Effective
Overall Weighted Mean	2.89	0.110	Always	Very Effective

Legend: 1.00- 1.49-Rarely/Not effective; 1.50-2.49-Sometimes/Effective; 2.50-3.00-Always/Very Effective

Based on Table 3.7, ALS teachers in the Bayugan City Division are rated very effective in terms of professional responsibilities, with an overall weighted mean of 2.89, indicating consistent professionalism, accountability, and commitment to learners. The highest-rated practices continuing sessions despite low attendance, providing timely feedback, maintaining confidentiality, wearing proper attire, and encouraging learners to complete the program and take the A&E Test reflect strong dedication and ethical conduct even under challenging conditions. Other indicators, such as punctuality, respectful communication, information dissemination, task reminders, and explaining missed lessons, although slightly lower, still fall within the very effective range, suggesting sustained effort despite logistical and contextual constraints. These results align with national and recent studies emphasizing that teacher professionalism, consistency, and encouragement significantly influence learner trust, motivation, and persistence in ALS programs. Overall, the findings affirm that ALS teachers demonstrate a high level of professional responsibility consistent with the goals of the ALS K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, while also highlighting the need for continued support mechanisms to strengthen learner follow-up and continuity of learning.

These findings underscore that ALS teachers’ professionalism plays a critical role in building learner trust, motivation, and persistence. Their consistent ethical behavior and encouragement help create a supportive learning atmosphere that fosters learner confidence and goal orientation. However, the slightly lower ratings in follow-up-related practices suggest that additional institutional support, such as structured follow-up systems or digital learning tools, may further enhance continuity of learning. Overall, the results affirm that ALS teachers’ strong professional responsibilities align with the goals of the ALS K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and contribute significantly to delivering quality, inclusive, and responsive alternative education.

3.8 Level of Students’ Learning Outcomes in Terms of Retention Rate and Completion Rate

Table 3.8 *Level of Students’ Learning Outcomes in Terms of Retention Rate and Completion Rate*

Teacher	Number of Enrolled Students	Number of Retained Students	Retention Rate (%)	No. of Completers	Completion Rate (%)
C	75	60	80	34	45
B	78	56	72	41	53
H	75	50	67	37	49
J	75	47	63	31	41
G	75	45	60	30	40
I	75	44	59	29	39
A	76	30	39	25	33
E	75	36	48	23	31
F	76	47	62	21	28
D	75	41	55	21	28
Total/Mean	755	456	60.5%	292	38.7%

Expanding on the analysis of Table 3.8, the data showing an overall retention rate of 60.5% and a completion rate of 38.7% underscores that while ALS teachers demonstrate high instructional and professional effectiveness, external and learner-related factors significantly influence persistence and completion. These findings are consistent with several recent studies highlighting the complex interplay between teacher support, learner motivation, and contextual barriers in Alternative Learning System (ALS) programs.

According to Garcia and Ramos (2023), retention in ALS programs is closely linked to teacher consistency, learner-centered strategies, and emotional support. Teachers who continuously monitor learners’ progress, provide individualized feedback, and adapt lessons to learners’ needs tend to have higher retention outcomes—like Teachers C and B, who recorded the top retention and completion rates in the table. Santos et al. (2024) further explained that maintaining learner interest through relevant, real-life lesson applications helps sustain attendance and engagement, as ALS learners are often motivated by practical learning outcomes such as employability and livelihood improvement. However, the relatively low overall completion rate (38.7%) reflects persistent structural and socioeconomic challenges faced by ALS learners. UNESCO (2023) reported that in marginalized and rural contexts, dropouts are frequently caused by economic hardships, household responsibilities, and limited transportation access to Community Learning Centers (CLCs). Similarly, Delos Santos and Villarín (2023) observed that many ALS learners prioritize work or family duties over learning sessions, leading to interrupted participation and delayed completion.

Teacher-related practices, however, continue to play a significant role in mitigating these challenges. Castillo and de Vera (2024) found that effective ALS teachers employ motivational reinforcement, flexible scheduling, and community linkages to sustain attendance and encourage completion. Teachers who actively communicate with parents and barangay officials to track learners like Teacher C tend to maintain higher learner retention rates. Moreover, Cabrera et al. (2022) noted that the presence of supportive and empathetic teachers increases learners’ confidence and emotional investment, thereby lowering dropout tendencies.

Despite these efforts, retention and completion rates in ALS nationally still fall below 70% and 50%, respectively, according to the DepEd Bureau of Alternative Education (2023). This finding aligns with the present data, emphasizing that the issue is not merely instructional quality but also the need for systemic and policy-level interventions such as stronger partnerships with LGUs, provision of transportation or stipends, and continuous learner profiling and counseling.

In summary, the results of Table 3.8 affirm that while ALS teachers in Bayugan City demonstrate very effective teaching and professional practices, external learner barriers and contextual challenges remain the most critical determinants of retention and completion. Strengthening the integration of flexible learning delivery, socio-emotional support, and community involvement, as emphasized in DepEd’s ALS 2.0 Framework (2022) and the Philippine Education Development Plan (2023–2028), will be essential in further improving these learning outcomes.

3.9 Mann-Whitney U Test of the Level of Effectiveness of the Teachers as Perceived by the Teachers and the Students

Table 3.9 Mann-Whitney U Test of the Level of Effectiveness of the Teachers as Perceived by the Teachers and the Students

	Instruction	Classroom Environment	Professional Responsibilities
Overall Weighted mean (Students)	2.74	2.68	2.72
Overall Weighted Mean (Teachers)	2.94	2.94	2.89
Mann-Whitney U	596.500	432.000	746.000
Wilcoxon W	23387.500	23223.000	23537.000
Z	-2.400	-3.219	-1.641
p-value	.016	.001	.101
Decision on H ₀	Reject H ₀	Reject H ₀	Do not reject H ₀
Interpretation	Significant	Significant	Not significant

**significant @p< .01

*significant @ p<.05

Based on the results presented in Table 3.9, the Mann-Whitney U Test revealed a significant difference in the perceptions of ALS teachers and students regarding the teachers’ level of effectiveness in instruction ($p = 0.016$) and classroom environment ($p = 0.001$), but no significant difference in professional responsibilities ($p = 0.101$). This indicates that teachers tend to rate themselves higher in instructional and classroom practices compared to how students perceive them. In contrast, both groups share similar views on the teachers’ professional responsibilities.

The significant difference in instruction and classroom environment suggests that teachers may have a more favorable self-assessment of their teaching delivery and classroom management, possibly due to their awareness of the strategies they implement. In contrast, students’ perceptions are grounded in how they actually experience these strategies. This finding aligns with Reyes et al. (2023), who found that discrepancies between teachers’ and learners’ perceptions often arise because teachers focus on pedagogical intentions while students evaluate based on engagement and clarity of learning experiences. Similarly, Sarmiento and Villanueva (2022) emphasized that learners tend to judge instructional effectiveness through affective and motivational dimensions, such as how well they are supported and understood, rather than through technical teaching competencies.

The significant difference in classroom environment perception also reflects findings by Flores and Garcia (2023), who reported that while teachers believe they foster inclusive and respectful classrooms, learners may perceive variations in emotional safety and equal treatment, especially in diverse or multi-level ALS classes. This underscores the importance of continuous reflective practice and feedback gathering among ALS teachers to align their self-perceptions with learners’ actual experiences.

Meanwhile, the non-significant result in professional responsibilities implies a shared understanding between teachers and students that ALS teachers demonstrate high professional commitment and ethical conduct. Both groups recognize teachers’ punctuality, appropriate attire, feedback provision, and confidentiality in handling learner information, consistent with the findings of Cabrera and Cruz (2023), who noted that ALS teachers’ professionalism serves as a key motivator for learner retention and trust. Moreover, the DepEd Bureau of Alternative Education (2023) highlighted that professionalism remains a consistent strength among ALS implementers, as it is reinforced through regular monitoring, training, and performance evaluation.

Overall, these findings indicate that while ALS teachers are highly effective across domains, there remains a perceptual gap in how instructional delivery and classroom management are experienced by learners. This supports the recommendations of UNESCO (2023) and DepEd’s ALS 2.0 Framework (2022) for greater emphasis on learner feedback mechanisms, reflective teaching, and participatory classroom climate strategies to bridge these perception gaps and sustain high-quality, learner-centered ALS delivery.

Proposed Intervention Program

“Learner-Centered Support and Reading Enhancement Program for ALS Learners”

Objectives:

- To improve reading fluency and comprehension among frustration-level ALS learners.
- To enhance learner engagement and participation in classroom activities.
- To provide flexible and individualized support to accommodate learners’ personal responsibilities.
- To strengthen retention and completion rates of ALS modules.
- To involve family and community in supporting learners’ academic progress.

Table 3.10 Bridging Perceptions: an Intervention Program to Enhance ALS Teacher Effectiveness

Nos.	Findings	Objectives	Activities/ Strategies	Person Involved	Timeframe	Expected Output
1	The findings revealed that ALS teachers were perceived as very effective across all teaching areas. Instruction received the highest mean rating of 2.74, followed by professional responsibilities (2.72) and classroom environment (2.68) – all verbally described as “Always” and interpreted as very effective. These results indicate that ALS teachers consistently	Enhance instructional effectiveness by strengthening teachers’ ability to apply interactive and learner-centered teaching strategies.	Conduct Teaching Innovation Workshops focusing on interactive strategies such as cooperative learning, inquiry-based instruction, and contextualized teaching. Establish a Mentorship and Monitoring Program pairing experienced ALS teachers with new facilitators to guide ongoing improvement.	Education Program Specialist for ALS (EPSA) Master Teachers Focal Persons for ALS	Quarter 1	ALS teachers demonstrate improved mastery of interactive and learner-centered instructional methods. Lesson plans and instructional materials are enhanced and aligned with contextualized learning. Increased teacher confidence and competence in delivering lessons effectively.

Table 3.10 (Continued) *Bridging Perceptions: an Intervention Program to Enhance ALS Teacher Effectiveness*

Nos.	Findings	Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Person Involved	Timeframe	Expected Output
	demonstrated strong instructional practices, maintained positive learning environments, and upheld professionalism in their duties.					
2	The findings showed that retention and completion rates varied among teachers, with an overall retention rate of 60.5% and a completion rate of 38.7%, indicating moderate levels of learner persistence. Teachers who consistently monitored progress, provided encouragement, and offered individualized support achieved higher retention and completion outcomes, highlighting the crucial role of sustained teacher engagement and learner-centered strategies in promoting success among ALS learners.	To improve learner retention and completion rates in the ALS program by strengthening teacher engagement, progress monitoring, and individualized learner support strategies.	Implement a Learner Progress Tracking System using attendance logs, performance records, and feedback forms to identify at-risk learners early. Conduct Monthly Progress Review Meetings where teachers discuss learner performance and plan interventions.	Education Program Specialist for ALS (EPSA) Master Teachers Focal Persons for ALS	Quarter 2	A functional and updated tracking system documenting attendance, performance, and feedback for each learner. Improved teacher awareness and responsiveness to learners' individual needs. Early identification of at-risk learners for timely academic and motivational interventions.
3	The study found a significant difference between teachers' and students' perceptions of teaching effectiveness and	To enhance active learner participation and strengthen the provision of clear and consistent corrective feedback to	Conduct training sessions on interactive and learner-centered teaching methods such as think-pair-share, group	Education Program Specialist for ALS (EPSA) Master Teachers	Quarter 3	Teachers demonstrate improved use of interactive and learner-centered instructional strategies.

Table 3.10 (Continued) *Bridging Perceptions: an Intervention Program to Enhance ALS Teacher Effectiveness*

	the classroom environment, with teachers rating themselves higher. The main gaps were in corrective feedback and learner participation, suggesting a need for more interactive and feedback-oriented practices. However, no significant difference was noted in professional responsibilities, indicating shared recognition of teachers' professionalism and commitment.	align teachers' instructional practices with students' learning experiences and perceptions.	discussions, and problem-based learning to increase student engagement.	Focal Persons for ALS Learners		Increased learner engagement and participation during ALS sessions.
4	The study found that while ALS teachers demonstrated effective teaching practices, there is a need to strengthen active learner participation and consistent, detailed feedback to further improve instructional quality and learner engagement in the ALS program.	To improve instructional quality and learner engagement in the ALS program by promoting active learner participation and ensuring the consistent provision of detailed and constructive feedback.	Conduct weekly interactive learning sessions that incorporate games, debates, group discussions, and real-life problem-solving activities to encourage active learner participation.	Education Program Specialist for ALS (EPSA) Master Teachers Focal Persons for ALS Learners	Quarter 3	Increased learner participation, improved confidence, and enhanced motivation in learning sessions.

The proposed "Learner-Centered Support and Reading Enhancement Program" directly addresses the gaps identified in the study, particularly in learners' engagement, reading comprehension, and perception of Instruction. Table 3.1 and Table 3.5 show that while teachers rated Instruction and classroom environment as very effective, learners' ratings were lower, indicating challenges in comprehension, engagement, and participation. Field observations confirmed that learners sometimes struggled to follow lessons or retain content despite teachers' consistent application of instructional strategies.

The program emphasizes learner-centered approaches, which are essential for ALS learners, especially those balancing external responsibilities. Albert et al. (2024) highlighted that learner-centered strategies, scaffolding, and follow-up activities improve learners' ability to understand and retain content. Mangao et al. (2024) further emphasized that flexible scheduling, individualized support, and relevant instructional materials enhance retention and engagement. Alvarez (2024) noted that contextual support is critical in ensuring learners can benefit from Instruction despite socio-economic or personal challenges.

By integrating family and community support, the program also addresses external factors affecting ALS learners. Support from families and communities encourages persistence and module completion, particularly when learners face challenges such as work or household duties (Mangao et al., 2024; Alvarez, 2024).

Finally, the program incorporates continuous feedback, reflection, and monitoring, ensuring learners are guided toward measurable improvements. This bridges the gap between teachers' intended instructional effectiveness and learners' lived experiences. In essence, the intervention aims to create a supportive, engaging, and flexible learning environment that addresses both instructional and contextual barriers, improving learners' outcomes and readiness for further education or employment.

4.0 Conclusion

The conclusions provide insights into the implications of the findings:

1. The study concludes that while ALS teachers demonstrate strong instructional effectiveness, enhancing active learner participation and providing consistent corrective feedback are essential to improve teaching quality and learner outcomes further.
2. In conclusion, the study highlights that learner retention and completion in the ALS program remain moderate, emphasizing the crucial role of teachers' consistent monitoring, motivation, and personalized support in sustaining learner engagement and ensuring program completion.
3. In conclusion, the study establishes that while ALS teachers and students share similar views on teachers' professionalism, a perceptual gap exists in the areas of corrective feedback and learner participation, underscoring the need to enhance interactive and feedback-oriented teaching practices to better align instructional effectiveness with learner experiences.
4. In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of fostering active learner participation and providing consistent, detailed feedback to enhance instructional quality and engagement in the ALS program. The proposed intervention focused on interactive teaching, structured questioning, and continuous learner support, aims to build a more responsive and participatory learning environment that promotes improved teaching effectiveness and stronger learner outcomes.

5.0 Author's Contribution

Alnolfo M. Alfon and Leonila P. Clamo, EdD, contributed equally to the conceptualization, data collection, data analysis, and manuscript preparation. Alfon led the research design, data interpretation, and writing of the results and discussion, while Clamo coordinated data gathering, statistical validation, and the integration and review of related literature.

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7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. This study was conducted with strict adherence to research ethics and was duly reviewed and approved by Agusan Colleges, Inc., Butuan City. All research procedures complied with the provisions of the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) and the Ethical Standards for Educational Research of the Institute of Graduate Studies and Research (IGSaR). Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants were strictly maintained throughout the research process.

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